

(in D_{3h} symmetry)⁷⁻⁹. A strong band at 1395 cm^{-1} observed in the above nitrocomplex (I) may be assigned as ν_3 mode of vibration of ionic nitro group. In $\text{Cu}(\text{BAPE})_2\text{SO}_4$ (III) two strong i.r. bands are observed at 1122 cm^{-1} (ν_3) and 619 cm^{-1} (ν_4), which suggests that the T_d symmetry of the SO_4^{2-} still holds¹⁰ in the complex. Again, the strong band observed at 1098 cm^{-1} in the complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{BAPE})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (II), may be considered ν_3 mode of vibration in free ClO_4^- ion in T_d symmetry.^{11,12}

Nickel (II) complexes : The reaction of $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$ with BAPE yields $\text{Ni}(\text{APE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (IV) instead of

We are not sure whether the initially formed unstable bluish green complex contain BAPE.

obvious that one azomethine bond is hydrolysed to yield the complex (IV). Although the insolubility of the complex suggests the polymeric nature of the complex; we are unable to provide any proof at this moment about polymerization. The reaction of BBE with $\text{Ni}(\text{SCN})_2$ also produced an insoluble complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BBE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (V), possibly polymeric in nature.

The observed μ_{eff} values for nickel (II) complexes (IV) and (V) is 3.02 and 3.29 B.M. respectively, which is in excellent agreement with the predicted magnetic moments for octahedral nickel (II) complexes.¹³⁻¹⁶ This geometry for the present nickel (II) complexes (IV) and (V) has also been substantiated by the electronic spectra of the complexes in nujol mull, although the spectral bands suggest much distortion from the idealized O_h point symmetry¹⁷.

The infrared spectrum of the complex $\text{Ni}(\text{APE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (IV) shows three bands at $3368(\text{s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{as}\text{NH}$), $3200(\text{br, s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_s\text{NH}$), and $1602(\text{s})\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (δNH). It reveals that in the complex (IV) the ligand APE contains a $-\text{NH}_2$ group which is coordinated to the metal ion. On the other hand, the complex $\text{Ni}(\text{BBE})(\text{SCN})_2$ (V) does not show any band for ν_{NH} or δNH . However, the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band appears around 1625 cm^{-1} for both the complexes. In the complexes (IV) and (V), three absorption bands appear at: ν_{CN} at $2140-2115\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1), ν_{CS} at $780-778\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3), and δNCS at $480-460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) regions. These assignments are made on the basis of previously published work.¹⁸⁻²⁴ The ν_1 and ν_2 bands are split into two peaks mainly in the form of shoulders, which is assignable to the bridging nature of NCS group (s) in the present complexes.¹⁸⁻²⁴ The position of ν_{as} band (as mentioned above) suggests the presence of N -bonded NCS ligand in these chelates. The appearance of multiple bands of medium intensity at $\text{Ca. } 475\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to δNCS vibration of N -bonded, bridged thiocyanate.^{20,23,25}

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Occurrence of $\Delta^{5,25}$ -Stigmastadien-3 β -ol and Erythrodiol in *Pristimera grahamii*

P. S. FERNANDES, E. J. DA SILVA, & V.V. NADKARNY,
Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, St. Xavier's College,
Bombay-400001.

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THE isolation of dulcitol and occurrence of Pristimerin an antibacterial principle, in the root bark of *Pristimera grahamii* has been reported¹⁻⁴. The present investigation deals with the isolation and characterisation of $\Delta^{5,25}$ -stigmastadien-3 β -ol and erythrodiol in the leaves of this plant. The 95% ethanolic Soxhlet extract of air-dried powdered leaves

was saponified and extracted with petroleum ether (40°-60°) : ether (50 : 50) mixture, then fractionated over a 3% deactivated alumina column.

The petroleum ether (40°-60°) : benzene (1 : 3) eluate yielded a compound which on crystallisation from methanol gave a m.p. 128°. Further its identity was established through chromatography over silica gel, reversed phase and argentation T.L.C. The spectral data of the compound was compared with the data reported in the literature⁵ for $\Delta^{5,2,5}$ -stigmastadien-3 β -ol and found to be identical with it. Elemental analysis gave the formula $C_{29}H_{48}O$.

The benzene : ether (3 : 1) eluate yielded another compound which on crystallisation from absolute ethanol gave a m.p. 288° (acetyl derivative m.p. 185°). The mass spectrum of this compound yielded a molecular weight of 442, showed a major fragmentation at m/e 234 and a strong peak m/e 411 (m-31). The I. R., NMR., data of the compound and its acetyl derivative were found to be identical with that of erythrodol^{6,7}. Elemental analysis of the compound gave a formula $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ and its acetyl derivative as $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$.

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Kinetics of the Reaction of cis-Dichlorodiammine Platinum (II) with Oxalate Ion in Aqueous Solution.

B. K. MAJI & S. K. SIDDHANTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan, West Bengal.

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CHEMICALS : cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂ was prepared by the method described by Keller¹ and Kauffman and Cowan². (Found : Pt, 65.34 ; Cl, 24.03 per cent. Calc. for cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ : Pt, 65.02 ; Cl, 23.62 per cent). Aqueous complex solution exhibited an absorption maximum at 300 nm and a minimum at

247 nm in agreement with the observations of Teggini, McCann and Smith³ and Reishus and Martin⁴. The product of the reaction, cis-Diammino (oxalate) Platinum (II), was synthesized under the same conditions that were used in the kinetic runs. (Found : Pt, 61.21 ; C₂O₄, 27.33 per cent. Calc. for cis-Pt (NH₃)₂ C₂O₄ : Pt, 61.49 ; C₂O₄ ; 27.74 per cent). The compound was insoluble in water and hence the absorption spectrum could not be obtained.

Kinetics : The kinetic study involved the potentiometric method. The reaction was initiated by adding ammonium oxalate solution to a thermostated solution of the cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂, kept at the desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The progress of the reaction between cis-Pt (NH₃)₂Cl₂ and ammonium oxalate was followed by measuring the increase in chloride ion concentration with the help of a Ag/AgCl electrode dipped into the reaction mixture using saturated calomel electrode as a reference one. The rates generally exhibited good reproducibility. In most of the experiments the progress of the reactions was followed until the reagent concentrations had decreased to about half their original values.

In a different set of experiments different excess concentrations of oxalate ion compared to the complex ion concentrations were used. It was found that the rate is independent of oxalate ion concentration and a first-order rate law, as defined by equation (1), was thus established,

$$\text{rate} = k[\text{cis-Pt (NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2] \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The experiments were conducted in solutions having different desired pH values adjusted by the addition of perchloric acid or sodium hydroxide solutions. The effect of temperature on the reactions have been studied at pH 6.2 and the values of ΔH^\ddagger , the enthalpy of activation and ΔS^\ddagger , the entropy of activation have been calculated from the usual Eyring equation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the first-order rate constants for various reaction conditions. The results indicated that $\Delta H^\ddagger = 18.2$ KCal/mole and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -18.9$ e.u. for the reaction.

TABLE 1—FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN CIS-PT(NH₃)₂CL₂ AND AMMONIUMOXALATE UNDER VARIOUS CONDITIONS

10^3 [cis-Pt(NH ₃) ₂ Cl ₂] M	10^3 [oxalate] M	Temp. °C	pH	$10^5 k \text{ Sec}^{-1}$
4.0	40.0	30	6.2	2.5
4.0	40	35	6.2	
4.0	80	35	6.2	
4.0	120	35	6.2	5.1
4.0	160	35	6.2	
4.0	40	40	6.2	9.0
4.0	80	45	6.2	13.0
4.0	80	50	6.2	22.6
4.0	80	35	3.2	4.3
4.0	80	35	8.4	4.6